

Dioxouranium(II) complexes of piperidylhydrazones

K. B. Gudasi* and T. R. Goudar

Department of Chemistry, Karnatak University, Dharwad-580 003, India

E-mail : kbgudasi@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received 3 August 2001, revised 1 November 2001, accepted 28 December 2001

New complexes of 1-piperidylhydrazones with dioxouranium(II) have been synthesized having stoichiometry 1 : 2 (metal : ligand). The spectral data show that the ligands are monobasic, tridentate in nature, coordinating through amide-O, imine-N and phenolate-O groups.

In continuation of our work on uranium complexes¹⁻³, we report here the syntheses and characterization of dioxouranium(II) complexes with the hydrazones derived from piperidine, viz. salicylidene-1-piperidylacetohydrazine (SPH), 5-methylsalicylidene-1-piperidylacetohydrazine (5-Me-SPH), 5-bromosalicylidene-1-piperidylacetohydrazine (5-Br-SPH), 5-chlorosalicylidene-1-piperidylacetohydrazine (5-Cl-SPH), 3-methoxysalicylidene-1-piperidylacetohydrazine (5-OMe-SPH), *o*-hydroxyacetophenone-1-piperidylacetohydrazine (*o*-OH-AcSPH).

Abbr.	R	R ₁
SPH	H	H
5-Me-SPH	5-Me	H
5-Br-SPH	5-Br	H
5-Cl-SPH	5-Cl	H
3-OMe-SPH	3-OMe	H
<i>o</i> -OH-Ac-SPH	H	CH ₃

Results and Discussion

The analytical data of the complexes (Table 1) indicate 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) stoichiometry. The complexes decompose without melting when heated above 330°. The molar conductance values suggest their non-electrolytic nature¹.

The medium intensity IR ligand band at 3220–3200 cm⁻¹ (N–H) remained unaffected on complexation. The ligand band at ~1675 cm⁻¹ (C=O) shifted to lower frequency in the complexes suggesting coordination through oxygen and hence the presence of ligand in ketonic form. The broad band around 2900 cm⁻¹ (intramolecular H-bonded OH) dis-

appeared on complexation, indicating the coordination of phenolic oxygen. This is further supported by a considerable positive shift of phenolic (C–O) group⁴. The band at 1610 cm⁻¹ (C=N) suffered a negative shift on complexation implying the coordination of azomethine nitrogen. This is further supported by the appearance of a band at ~650 cm⁻¹ (U–N)⁵. The band at 920–890 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of the complexes is ascribed to $\nu_{3\text{asym}}$ and one at 820 cm⁻¹ to $\nu_{1\text{sym}}$ O=U=O stretching vibration, suggesting² the linear nature of UO₂.

Table 1. Analytical and conductance data of UO₂ complexes with piperidine hydrazones*

Compd.	U% Found (Calcd.)	Λ_M $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$
[UO ₂ (SPH) ₂ .2H ₂ O]	29.02 (29.17)	14
[UO ₂ (5-Me-SPH) ₂ .2H ₂ O]	28.02 (28.20)	16
[UO ₂ (5-Cl-SPH) ₂ .2H ₂ O]	26.69 (26.89)	14
[UO ₂ (5-Br-SPH) ₂ .2H ₂ O]	24.24 (24.44)	18
[UO ₂ (3-OMe-SPH) ₂ .2H ₂ O]	27.00 (27.17)	20
[UO ₂ (<i>o</i> -OH-AcSPH) ₂ .2H ₂ O]	28.10 (28.20)	16
[UO ₂ (<i>o</i> -OH-NapPH) ₂ .2H ₂ O]	25.80 (25.98)	18

*All the compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analysis.

The complexes exhibit broad and weak reflectance spectral bands which may probably due to greater stability of O–U–O species⁶. The bands at 325–330 and 355–360 nm are assigned to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions²⁻⁷. The band at 425–430 nm is attributed to $^1E_g \rightarrow ^3\Pi_4$ transition, typical of O–U–O symmetric stretching frequency for the first excited state⁸. The bands at 445–460 nm is due to the vibration of UO₂^{II} group.

The PMR spectrum of 5-bromo-salicylidene-1-piperidylacetohydrazine showed signals at δ 1.5 (6H, $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-$), 2.4 (4H, $-\text{CH}_2-\text{N}-\text{CH}_2-$), 3.0 (2H, $>\text{N}-\text{CH}_2$). The signal at δ 6.5 (d) is assigned to H-C₆ and 6.8–7.1 (m) to H-C₃ and H-C₄ of salicylaldehyde moiety. Azomethine proton was observed at δ 8.05 (s), while the NH proton at δ 8.95. The broad singlet at δ 12.9 is due to *o*-hydroxy proton. The broadening of the signal is due to strong hydrogen bonding. In the spectrum of the complex, the resonance due to *o*-hydroxy proton disappeared, indicating the deprotonation. The resonance due to NH shifted downfield to δ 9.3. The appearance of NH resonance indicates the presence of ligand in ketonic form and the downfield shift implies its deshielding. This suggests the coordination of adjacent carbonyl group. The downfield shift of azomethine proton suggests its coordination.

Experimental

The chemicals used were of reagent grade and purified before use by standard methods.

Synthesis of ligands : A mixture of piperidino-*N*-acetyl (0.01 mol) and substituted salicylaldehydes or *o*-hydroxyacetophenone (0.01 mol) was refluxed in ethanol for 2 h and the solution then concentrated. The pale yellow crystalline solid that separated on cooling was crystallized : SPH, m.p. 107°; 5-Me-SPH, 120°; 5-Br-SPH, 120°; 5-Cl-SPH, 155°; 3-OMe-SPH, 187°; *o*-OH-Ac-SPH, 186°.

Synthesis of complexes : Uranyl acetate dihydrate (0.001 mol) in ethanol (15 ml) was added to a solution of hydrazones (0.002 mol) in ethanol (15 ml) and the resulting

red solution was refluxed for 1 h. The solution was then evaporated to a syrupy mass and triturated with petroleum ether. The resulting solid was washed and dried over fused calcium chloride.

Uranium was determined gravimetrically as U₃O₈. C, H, and N were determined using a Perkin-Elmer 240 analyzer. Molar conductance was measured (10^{-3} M concentration in DMF) using an Elico CM-82 conductivity bridge. Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 783 spectrophotometer, diffused reflectance spectra on a Cary d-2390 spectrophotometer and PMR spectra on a EM-390 (90 MHz) spectrometer.

References

1. K. B. Gudasi and T. R. Goudar, *Pol. J. Chem.*, 1990, **73**, 385; P. B. Maravalli, K. B. Gudasi and T. R. Goudar, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2000, **39**, 1087.
2. T. R. Goudar, S. M. Shindagi and G. S. Nadagouda, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1987, **64**, 636.
3. S. D. Dhumwad, K. B. Gudasi and T. R. Goudar, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1994, **33**, 320, 782; T. R. Goudar, G. S. Nadagouda and K. B. Gudasi, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1993, **32**, 1075; G. M. Shashidhara and T. R. Goudar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2001, **78**, 360.
4. N. S. Biradar, M. D. Patil and T. R. Goudar, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1975, **37**, 1437.
5. T. M. Aminabhavi, N. S. Biradar, V. L. R. Goudar, D. E. Hofman and W. E. Rudzinski, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1986, **121**, 45.
6. J. T. Bell, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1969, **31**, 703.
7. A. Symal and M. R. Maurya, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1985, **24**, 836.
8. S. P. McGlynn and J. K. Smith, *J. Mol. Spectrosc.*, 1961, **6**, 164.